

University of Luxembourg

Multilingual. Personalised. Connected.

Multilingualism and digital methods teaching: Conceiving pedagogical materials in a multilingual-first approach

1. Our Approach: A Multilingual-first Tutorial Using Tropy
2. Multilingualism and DH Educational Resources
3. Conclusion

Our Approach: A Multilingual-first Tutorial using Tropy

- Douglas McRae - Postdoctoral Research Fellow, RRCHNM - Douglas coordinates educational outreach and support for the digital research tool Tropy in the Americas - EN, ES
- Anita Lucchesi - Postdoctoral Researcher, C²DH - Anita coordinates education outreach and support for Tropy in the lusophone countries plus IT and EN
- Sofia Papastamkou - Postdoctoral Researcher, C²DH - Sofia is in charge of the teaching platform Ranke.2 - (GR) FR, EN

Online open access tutorial(s) to enable historians and other fellow humanists to gather, organize, annotate and prepare for analysis and dissemination digital photos of primary sources with Tropy software:

ES: *Del caos hacia el orden, gestionar fuentes primarias digitalizadas con Tropy*

FR: *Du chaos à l'ordre, la gestion des sources primaires numérisées avec Tropy*

PT: *Do caos à ordem, gestão de fontes primárias digitalizadas com Tropy*

An open-source tool for managing archival photos and research images.

Conceived by researchers for researchers, RRCHNM, George Mason Uni & C²DH

Website: <https://tropy.org/> – Current version: 1.13.1

Documentation: <https://docs.tropy.org/>

Support Forum: <https://forums.tropy.org/>

YouTube Channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@tropy>

Twitter: @tropy (<https://twitter.com/tropy>)

Tropy in a Nutshell

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Why Tropy: Digitization of Historians' Research Practice

"We've changed our ways, but along the way we've unwittingly created new problems of organization and analysis of our effectively limitless personal digital archives. Where the historian's research program once imposed some kind of order, however idiosyncratic, on an archive (itself already orderly, in all likelihood), the imperative to photograph as much as possible dissociates objects from context, atomizes documents into fragments, promises abundance but delivers disorder. There's no technological quick fix, and as yet no new professional norms to offer guidance, but my hope is that this little piece of software will serve as a first lifeline for researchers adrift on a silent sea of JPGs."

Sean Takats, "Tropy", blog post, *Quintessence of Ham*, 26/10/2017, <http://quintessenceofham.org/2017/10/26/tropy/>

- Effectively organize and annotate image files of primary sources as research data
- Learn the importance and correct use of metadata adapted to one's own primary sources and historical research
- Manage research data in a way to enhance future analysis and presentation

Through the prism of (digital) source criticism.

- A tutorial directly conceived in 3 languages: ES, PT, FR
- Skipping the translation: not an original in one language replicated or adapted to the two other languages of our choice
- A main body jointly conceived around the software and its use
- 3 different datasets each adapted to the target languages but also open to the world

"Our idea is to conceive the main structure of the tutorial together, and in this sense we are all co-authors of the three tutorials. Then, each one of us will be responsible (and thus be the main author) for writing it in one language: McRae for ES, Papastamkou for FR, Lucchesi for PT. Each tutorial will have adapted datasets, present a historical problem and include references. Our datasets, however, can appeal to an international audience as well either by the type of source (for example visual) or by the ability to correspond to approaches of transnational or connected histories. In this sense, we propose three associated tutorials, in which all three can be considered as original versions."

Sources from Sección Civil-Esclavos (1700-1858)-Academia Nacional de Historia de Venezuela, PDF files of **digitized legal records**, initiative of the Red Historia Venezuela. This collection consists of a series of volumes making up the judicial section of the Afro-Venezuelan slaves, collection held by the Academia Nacional de la Historia in Caracas, containing **legal cases (expedientes judiciales) related to slavery from the colonial and early post-independence periods (1700-1858)**.

[Sección Civil-Esclavos \(1700-1858\)-Academia Nacional de Historia de Venezuela](#)

[Red Historia Venezuela](#)

Posters of the French May 1968, Gallica (image files of visual primary sources)

Gallica: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/>

Varied sources from the project “Memorial dos Náufragos”, initiative of the Grupo de Estudos do Tempo Presente on the developments leading to the torpedoing of merchant ships by the German submarine U-507 between Bahia and Sergipe in August 1942. This project's collection features replicas, reproductions and transcriptions of original documents of diverse provenance, some digitised by the project members themselves and some gathered from online available repositories of digitized sources (i.e. photos, newspaper articles, ego documents, maps, etc.).

[Grupo de Estudos do Tempo Presente](#)

Multilingualism and DH Educational Resources

Why a Multilingual(-first) approach

- A need for non-EN tutorials
- An ability to do so: multilingual infrastructures (software, editorial relays)
- A will to do so: community engagement

We **need** (Tropy) tutorials in our working languages

=> All three authors have been / are engaged in DH methods/tools training activities in ES-, PT- FR-speaking higher education, editorial, professional environments

=> The ability to teach and write in non-EN language was a key skill for profiling the Outreach Coordinators for Tropy in its last development and outreach phase (2022-2023).

Is translation enough?

=> Hidden wisdom of the Programming Historian paradigm: ES (2017), FR (2019), PT (20121)

[Guidelines for writing for a global audience](#), 2018

See also: Sichani et al. 2019

Typology of translations, PH

1. Linguistic changes: instructions mainly - the material used (data, code) is not translated
2. Expressive changes: explanation, extra bibliography, code and/or partially adapted material
3. Substantial changes: correction, update, addition/omission, adaptation, versioning, change of material (e.g. dataset) => co-authorship?

Isasi & Rojas Castro 2021; Isasi & Quiroga 2021

Tropy

- first made available in English (2016/2017), then followed by French and German
- currently, user interface available in 9 languages: English, French, German, Italian, Japanese, Chinese, Spanish and Portuguese, Brazilian Portuguese + Ukrainian currently in beta phase (expected for v. 1.14.0)
- possibility to add more via [community engagement](#) using Transifex

Tropy Language Locales (screenshot 29 May 2023, Windows 10, Tropy v. 1.13.1)

Programming Historian (EN, ES, FR, PT)

<https://programminghistorian.org/>

OpenMethods <https://openmethods.dariah.eu/about/>

DARIAH-Campus <https://campus.dariah.eu/>

#dariahTeach <https://teach.dariah.eu/>

Ranke.2 <https://ranke2.uni.lu/>

=> Part of “the invisible college” (Crymble 2021)

Between need and choice:

- first write in (other) central* (FR) and (semi)peripheral languages (ES, PT)
- then translate into the hyper-central* (EN) if necessary

* Center/periphery languages as per (Heilbron 1999)

Conclusion

- three connected tutorials, all of which can be considered as original versions
- what implications for (co)authorship and peer review?
- English as lingua franca and translation integrated in the process of authoring but not in the outcome
- reverse the direction of the translation of the output (English as target-language)

Thank you for your attention!

@s_papastamkou

@alucchesi

@dv_mcrae

www.c2dh.uni.lu